

Patterns of Chief Complaints in Breast Disorders and Their Association with Diagnosis and Family History

Sahar Muayad Abdulwahhab

Baghdad Health Directorate-Al-Karkh, Baghdad, Iraq

Taif Raad Abbas Abid Ali

Babylon health directorate, Babylon, Iraq

Alaa Mohammed Altameemi

Baghdad Health Directorate-Al-Karkh, Baghdad, Iraq

Abstract

Background: Breast disorders represent a major cause of morbidity among women and account for a substantial proportion of visits to breast clinics. The pattern of presenting symptoms may reflect underlying pathology and is influenced by demographic and familial factors. Understanding the relationship between chief complaints, diagnostic outcomes, and family history is essential for improving early detection and clinical management of breast diseases. **Objective:** This study aimed to analyze the patterns of chief complaints among women with breast disorders and to examine their association with diagnostic categories and family history. **Methods:** A retrospective observational study was conducted at the Breast Clinic of Al-Karkh Teaching Hospital, Baghdad, from June 2022 to June 2023. Medical records of 267 female patients were reviewed. Data on age, family history, menstrual cycle history, chief complaint, and final diagnosis were collected. Diagnoses were classified into benign and malignant lesions. **Results:** The mean age of patients was 47.7 ± 11.3 years, with 72.7% aged over 40 years. Most patients had no family history of breast cancer (58.4%), and irregular menstrual cycles were observed in 53.2%. Mastalgia and consultation were the most common complaints among patients with benign lesions, whereas a palpable breast mass was the predominant presenting symptom in malignant cases (63.2%). Significant associations were found between chief complaints and diagnosis, as well as between family history and presenting symptoms ($P < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** Distinct patterns of chief complaints were associated with diagnostic outcomes and family history. Recognition of symptom profiles may enhance early detection strategies and improve clinical assessment of breast disorders.

Introduction

Breast disorders represent one of the most common reasons for healthcare visits among women worldwide, encompassing a broad spectrum of benign and malignant conditions. The clinical presentation of breast diseases varies widely, with patients reporting symptoms such as breast pain, palpable masses, nipple discharge, axillary swelling, or attending clinics for routine screening and consultation. Understanding the patterns of chief complaints is essential for early detection, accurate diagnosis, and effective management of breast diseases, particularly in regions where late presentation remains a significant challenge [1,2]. Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed

cancer among women globally and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality. According to the Global Cancer Observatory, breast cancer accounted for over 2.3 million new cases and approximately 685,000 deaths worldwide in 2020, with increasing incidence reported in low- and middle-income countries [3]. In the Middle East and Iraq, breast cancer remains the most common female malignancy, often presenting at advanced stages due to limited awareness, cultural barriers, and inadequate screening programs [4,5]. However, benign breast diseases constitute the majority of breast clinic visits and often present with symptoms that overlap with malignant conditions, complicating clinical decision-making [6]. The chief

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Keywords:

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complaint at presentation plays a crucial role in guiding diagnostic pathways. For instance, a palpable breast mass is frequently associated with malignant lesions, whereas mastalgia is more commonly linked to benign conditions such as fibrocystic changes or hormonal fluctuations. Similarly, nipple discharge and axillary swelling may indicate either benign or malignant pathology depending on associated clinical and imaging findings [7,8]. Therefore, analyzing the relationship between presenting symptoms and final diagnoses can provide valuable insights into risk stratification and early detection strategies. Family history is a well-established risk factor for breast cancer, particularly among women with first-degree relatives affected by the disease. Genetic predisposition, including mutations in BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes, significantly increases lifetime breast cancer risk and influences clinical presentation and disease severity [9]. Moreover, women with a positive family history are more likely to seek screening and medical consultation, which may affect the pattern of chief complaints observed in clinical settings [10]. The study aims to analyze the patterns of chief complaints among women with breast disorders and examine their association with diagnostic categories and family history in patients attending the breast clinic at Al-Karkh Teaching Hospital in Baghdad.

Method

This retrospective observational study was conducted at the Breast Clinic of Al-Karkh Teaching Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq, over a one-year period from June 2022 to June 2023. A total of 267 female patients who attended the breast clinic during the study period were included. All available medical records were reviewed comprehensively to extract relevant clinical and demographic data. The collected variables included age (in years), family history of breast cancer or other malignancies, menstrual cycle history, chief complaint

at presentation, and final clinical diagnosis of breast disease. Age was categorized into two groups (≤ 40 years and > 40 years). Family history was classified as first-degree relatives, second-degree relatives, history of other malignancies, or no family history. Menstrual cycle history was categorized as regular, irregular, or menopausal status. Diagnoses were grouped into benign and malignant breast lesions according to clinical, imaging, and pathological findings documented in patient records. The chief complaint was defined as the primary symptom or reason for presentation to the breast clinic, including breast mass, mastalgia, nipple discharge, axillary swelling, follow-up visits, or consultation/screening. Breast disease diagnosis was considered the dependent variable, while chief complaint and family history were treated as independent variables. Inclusion criteria comprised all female patients who presented to the breast clinic during the study period, regardless of age or diagnosis. No exclusion criteria were applied to ensure comprehensive representation of clinical presentations. Data were entered and analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics, expressed as frequencies, percentages, and mean \pm standard deviation where appropriate. The chi-square test was employed to evaluate the association between categorical variables, particularly the relationship between breast disease diagnosis and chief complaint, as well as between family history and chief complaint. A P-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Age of patients 47.7 ± 11.3 years, the peak of patients is age group more than 40 years old 194 (72.7%). 156 (58.4%) of patients have no family history and 142 (53.2%) of patients have irregular menstrual cycle. (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution Characteristics of Patients

variables		frequency	percentage
Age group (years)	≤ 40	73	27.3
	> 40	194	72.7
Family history	1st relative	30	11.2
	2nd relative	55	20.6
	history of other malignancies	26	9.7
History of menstrual cycle	no	156	58.4
	Irregular	142	53.2
	Menopause	45	16.9
	Regular	80	30.0

Table 2 demonstrated that there is significant association between diagnosis and Chief complains, 41.2% and 32.8% of patients with Benign lesions have

chief complain mastalgia and come only for consultation. While 63.2% of patients with Malignant lesion have chief complain come to check mass appear.

Table 2: Association between Diagnosis and Chief Complains

DX	Chief complains						Total	P-value
	axillary swelling	follow up	mass	mastalgia	nipple discharge	consultation		
Benign	8	6	33	95	12	75	229	0.0001
	3.5%	2.6%	14.4%	41.5%	5.2%	32.8%	100.0%	
Malignant	0	0	24	6	0	8	38	
	0.0%	0.0%	63.2%	15.8%	0.0%	21.1%	100.0%	

Table 3 demonstrated that there is significant association between family history and Chief complains, 41.8% and 42.3% of patients with second degree of family history and family history of other

carcinoma have chief complain mastalgia. While 43.3% and 30.8% of patients with first degree of family history and no history of carcinoma come for screening.

Table 3: Association between Family History and Chief Complains

FH	Chief complains						Total	P-value
	axillary swelling	follow up	mass	mastalgia	nipple discharge	consultation		
1 st	1	2	4	10	0	13	30	0.0001
	3.3%	6.7%	13.3%	33.3%	0.0%	43.3%	100.0%	
2 nd	1	1	13	23	2	15	55	
	1.8%	1.8%	23.6%	41.8%	3.6%	27.3%	100.0%	
Other	2	0	5	11	1	7	26	
Ca	7.7%	0.0%	19.2%	42.3%	3.8%	26.9%	100.0%	
No	4	3	35	57	9	48	156	
History	2.6%	1.9%	22.4%	36.5%	5.8%	30.8%	100.0%	

Discussion

This study provides insight into the clinical patterns of breast complaints and their association with diagnostic outcomes and family history among women attending a breast clinic in Baghdad. The mean age of patients was 47.7 ± 11.3 years, with nearly three-quarters of cases occurring in women older than 40 years. This finding is consistent with regional and global reports indicating that breast diseases, particularly malignant lesions, are more prevalent in middle-aged and older women. Similar age distributions have been reported in studies from developing countries, where the peak incidence of breast disorders occurs after the fourth decade of life [11,12]. In the present study, most patients had no family history of breast cancer (58.4%), while irregular menstrual cycles were observed in more than half of the participants (53.2%). These findings highlight the multifactorial nature of breast diseases, where hormonal and reproductive factors may play a significant role alongside genetic predisposition. Previous research has shown that menstrual irregularities and hormonal disturbances are associated with benign breast conditions, while family history remains a strong risk factor for malignant breast lesions [13,14]. A significant association was observed between diagnosis and chief complaints. Mastalgia and consultation visits were the predominant presenting complaints among patients with benign breast lesions,

whereas the majority of malignant cases presented with a palpable breast mass. This pattern aligns with earlier studies demonstrating that breast pain is more frequently linked to benign conditions, while a breast lump is the most common presenting symptom of breast cancer [15,16]. These findings underscore the importance of symptom-based clinical assessment in differentiating benign from malignant breast conditions and guiding diagnostic investigations. Furthermore, the study revealed a significant association between family history and chief complaints. Patients with second-degree family history or history of other malignancies most commonly presented with mastalgia, whereas those with first-degree family history and those without any family history were more likely to seek screening or consultation. This observation suggests that family history may influence health-seeking behavior and symptom perception among women. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies, which demonstrated that women with a positive family history are more likely to participate in screening programs and seek early medical advice [17,18].

Conclusion

Breast disorders were most common in women over 40 years. Mastalgia was mainly associated with benign lesions, while a palpable mass was the most frequent symptom in malignant cases. Significant relationships

were found between chief complaints, diagnosis, and family history, highlighting the value of symptom patterns in early detection and clinical assessment of breast diseases.

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